

The Basic Experience and Enlightenment of the Construction of Ideological Discourse Right in the Seventy Years since the Founding of New China

Yong cao ¹

¹(College of Marxism, Anhui University of Finance and Economics, China)

ABSTRACT: The Communist Party of China attaches great importance to the construction of ideological discourse power. As a superstructure, ideology is always presented and expressed in a certain discourse. The formation and development of ideological discourse right have distinct historical characteristics. Combing the practice of ideological discourse right construction in the 70 years since the founding of New China will help to promote the innovation and development of ideological discourse right construction in the new era.

KEYWORDS: ideology, discourse power, mass media

Project support: 2019 Anhui Social Science Planning Project: Xi Jinping's micro propagation research on socialism with Chinese characteristics in the new era (AHSKY2019D047)

I. Introduction

The party's overall and ideological work is fundamental. General secretary Xi Jin ping pointed out the realistic problems of "the struggle for ideological field in China still needs to be solved" in China's socialism with Chinese characteristics in the nineteen major reports of the party, and put forward the realistic task of "continuously enhancing the leading power and discourse power of ideology" in the new era of socialism with Chinese characteristics [1]. This shows that the Central Committee of CPC, with the core of general secretary Xi Jinping, attaches great importance to strengthening the construction of the discourse power of socialist ideology. Historical materialism holds that history, present and future are interlinked. It is of great theoretical and practical significance to summarize the practice and basic experience of the Communist Party of China in promoting the construction of Marxist ideological discourse in the new era.

1, A review of the construction of ideological discourse power since the founding of new China

1.1 Constructing discourse system to realize the awesome power of ideological discourse power.

As the premise of discourse power, discourse system is the external expression of value system and has distinct ideological characteristics. From the perspective of the history of the construction of the theoretical discourse system of the Sinicization of Marxism, the theoretical discourse system of the Sinicization of Marxism has evolved in turn, and the development of discourse has gone through the process of classic theory - Sinicization of theory - Chinese theory[2]. In the 70 years since the founding of new China, the construction of the discourse system of the theory of Sinicization of Marxism has focused on answering the following basic questions: what is Marxism and how to treat Marxism; what is socialism, what kind of socialism to build and how to build socialism; what kind of party to build and how to build the party, what kind of development to achieve and how

to develop it; what kind of party to build and how to develop it; What kind of socialism with Chinese characteristics should we adhere to and develop in the new era, and how to adhere to and develop socialism with Chinese characteristics have completed the transformation from the revolutionary party ideology of "fighting for the world" to the ruling party ideology of "sitting on the world"[3]. In terms of the specific practice of the construction of ideological discourse right in the 70 years since the founding of new China, the discourse system has been constructed around the goal of China's modernization construction, and the development strategies of "four modernizations", "three steps" and "new three steps" of industry, agriculture, national defense and science and technology have been put forward. The new road of industrialization, informatization, urbanization and agricultural modernization with Chinese characteristics has been adhered to, Building a well-off society in an all-round way, the strategic goal of "two centenaries", the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation and the Chinese dream, etc. The mainstream ideology discourse system is constantly enriched and developed. The logical starting point of the construction of ideological discourse system is practice. In the face of new problems in the practice of socialism with Chinese characteristics, we should constantly overcome and discard those old discourses that lag behind the development of the times and practice, and constantly absorb new discourses that reflect the trend of social development and the latest social practice. The construction of ideological discourse system is the self completion of socialist cultural construction Goodness and development is an important way for the mainstream ideology to expand its discourse space. The perfection of discourse theory system is the dominant sign of the maturity and depth of the mainstream ideology[4].

1.2 Criticizing wrong social thoughts and strengthening the cohesion of ideological discourse power

Lenin pointed out that Marxism "has to fight every step of its life"[5]. In the early days of the founding of new China, the Communist Party of China consolidated the discourse power of socialist ideology by criticizing non socialist ideology. The existence of these non socialist ideologies seriously hindered the people's enthusiasm for building socialism. In view of the fact that there are still many remnants and strong influences of feudal thought in Chinese society, Mao Zedong proposed to carry out in-depth criticism of feudal thought. While carrying out the socialist industrial and commercial transformation, he also carried out criticism of bourgeois idealism. By carrying out the ideological and cultural criticism movement, he armed people's minds with Marxism Leninism and made the majority of Party members and the people recognize it We have known and mastered the important role of Marxism Leninism and Mao Zedong thought, and understood the party's line and guiding ideology, so as to lay a good ideological and cultural foundation for the completion of socialist transformation and socialist construction.

Since the reform and opening up, we have frequently carried out ideological and cultural exchanges with western capitalist countries. Western ideology has been implicitly infiltrated in the cooperation and communication in various fields. Deng Xiaoping pointed out in his speech at the second plenary session of the 12th CPC Central Committee: "some comrades are keen on talking about human value, humanitarianism and so-called alienation, and their interest is not in criticizing capital We are criticizing socialism instead of socialism. " Comrade Jiang ze min stressed that we must actively criticize the attack against Marxism and not let it go.

With the development of mobile network, social thoughts such as Neo liberalism, democratic socialism, universal axiology and constitutionalism spread their voices through network channels, which makes it more difficult for ordinary people, especially young people, to distinguish right from wrong.

To criticize all kinds of non Marxist ideologies, we need to carefully analyze and study their theoretical and practical foundations. The New Liberalists try to change the correct direction of China's reform, change China's basic economic system, and vigorously advocate and publicize the policy propositions with the main contents of economic privatization, complete marketization and absolute liberalization. For example, in view of the wrong argument of "the end of ideology" in the era of big data, this paper analyzes the fundamental differences between the two kinds of social ideologies from the aspects of international strategy, economic foundation,

political perspective and cultural tendency, so as to better deal with the new security challenges brought by neoliberalism to China's socialist ideology[6].

The Communist Party of China has proposed that in the process of the construction of the discourse power in the ideological field, we must draw a clear line with the non Marxist social thoughts, and be alert to the infiltration and influence of the non Marxist social thoughts.

1.3 Adhere to the position construction and consolidate the influence of ideological discourse power

The generation and establishment of discourse power of mainstream ideology cannot do without discourse communication. He stressed: "in order to overthrow a regime, we must first create public opinion and do ideological work. This is true of the revolutionary class, and so is the counter revolutionary class." [7]

As an important part of social institutions, mass media organizations participate in the construction of social system. Language is born with the function of carrying and transmitting certain ideology, and the development of ideology is also born closely related to language. If ideological discourse only stops at the internal Abstract speculative link and lacks the external specific language expression, it will inevitably fall into the discourse dilemma of "no reason, no way and no transmission", thus greatly reducing the discourse power of ideology.[8] The construction of ideological discourse power must attach importance to the position construction of discourse communication.

Under the condition of traditional media, ideological discourse mainly carries out ideological propaganda and education to ordinary people through newspapers, radio, television, books and other communication positions. It is a one-way monologue discourse communication mode from top to bottom and from point to surface. In this communication mode, the audience of discourse not only accepts the ideological methods, values and behavior advocated by the state, but also accepts the ideology, values and behavior advocated by the state, Basically, it is seldom influenced by other discourses and ideological systems, and the audience has a high acceptance of the discourse and a strong sense of identity. "We should absorb constructive opinions in time, help people in time with difficulties, publicize and introduce people who don't know the situation in time, clear up vague understanding in time, resolve complaints in time, and guide and correct wrong opinions in time. We should make the Internet a new platform for communication with the masses, a new way to understand the masses, get close to the masses, and solve problems for the masses It is a new channel to carry forward people's democracy and accept people's supervision.

In today's China, the development of network media not only reconstructs the traditional media pattern, but also increasingly becomes the fermentation place of social public opinion. The audience scale of traditional media is shrinking, and the living space is constantly squeezed by network media. The social communication practice field on which the discourse power of Marxist ideology depends is undergoing the transition from "traditional media" to "network media" New situation. People's daily social activities increasingly rely on wechat, microblog, Tencent and other network media, "the Internet has increasingly become the source of public opinion, the distribution center of information dissemination, the main position of ideological confrontation, and the biggest" variable "of people's social life." [9]

In order to adapt to the rapid development of network media, the construction of ideological discourse position should actively promote the development of media integration, and the mainstream media should be the leader, combine the content authority advantage of mainstream media with the communication effect advantage of network media, create ideological discourse communication position with diverse forms, advanced means and international competitiveness, and promote the formation of ideological discourse position with the thinking of integration The integrated organizational structure, communication system and management system, give full

play to the unique advantages of various media, and form a multi-level and three-dimensional cooperative assimilation information communication position mode.

1.4 From home to abroad, expand the radiation of ideological discourse power

As an important dimension of human survival and development, space is not only the extensive place of material existence, but also the congenital control of human survival and development. Any ruling class should rely on ideology to give universality to the theory reflecting its own interests. The construction of this universality depends on the integration of ideology into real life and relying on objective space.

Due to the influence of the cold war thinking and the dogmatization of Marxism, in the early days of the founding of new China, the Communist Party of China comprehensively criticized many achievements beneficial to human civilization in capitalist society, regarded the Western values and ideological culture as a flood of water and beasts, and carried out ideological construction and propaganda in a completely closed state. The "going out" strategy, ideology is completely closed in the development, to a certain extent, also led to our country in the construction of ideological discourse power of complacency, in a passive defensive state, lack of communication and confrontation with other countries' ideology. At the same time, the construction of socialist country has just started in this period, from the material foundation to cultural construction are in a relatively weak period, this situation can not provide the necessary guarantee for the spread of socialist ideological discourse to the world.

After the reform and opening up, the Communist Party of China has realized the gap between China and foreign countries in the construction of ideological discourse right, especially in the western developed capitalist countries. It has begun to transform the advanced achievements of the theory and events of western ideological discourse right into its own benefits, creating a new stage in the construction of ideological discourse right.

Publicizing the theory of socialism with Chinese characteristics is an important turn in the construction of socialist ideological discourse power. The relationship between China and the world is undergoing historic changes. China is stepping into the center of the world stage, and the world needs to better understand China. In recent years, the international community has made different voices about the development of Chinese society, summarizing the Chinese model as "state capital". The spread of Chinese ideological discourse system is conducive to explaining China's development strategy to the world, telling China's story, explaining Chinese characteristics, safeguarding the interests of the country, and establishing a good image of China's development, so as to help the international community better understand and recognize China's development.

The Communist Party of China is a political party striving for the happiness of the Chinese people and the cause of human progress. The Communist Party of China is the largest ruling party in the world. The Communist Party of China should not be absent from the theoretical and practical development of the global ideological discourse construction, let alone lack China's voice on major issues related to human development.

China's idea of building a community of shared future for mankind is based on the successful practice of China's development path. It is not an illusory unification of China's national interests and the interests of all mankind, but a substantive provision of China's plan and wisdom for global governance.[10]

1.5 In line with the needs of the audience, enhance the persuasion of ideological discourse

All the ideological achievements of human society need not only to be expressed and recorded by means of language, but also to be accumulated and inherited by means of language. The effectiveness of discourse expression is one of the important factors that determine whether the ideological discourse power can be accepted by the audience. If the expression of ideological discourse still stays in the empty political propaganda and rigid preaching, it will inevitably lose its function of inspiring, integrating and condensing the masses.

In the process of promoting the spread of Marxist ideological discourse, the Communist Party of China is good at grasping the psychological needs of the masses, adapting the discourse content to the interests of the masses, and letting the masses "listen". Comrade Mao Zedong believed that every thought and every sentence of the Communists should reflect "the thoughts and emotions of millions of people" and the voice of the people. If Communists really want to do propaganda, they have to look at the objects, and they have to think about who they want to see and listen to their articles, speeches, conversations and writings [11]. In the new era of reform and opening up, Deng Xiaoping put forward such ideological discourse as "realizing common prosperity", "poverty is not socialism" and "three benefits", which innovated Marxist ideological discourse and enhanced the appeal of discourse in the concern for the interests of the people. Since the eighteen Party's Congress, the Central Committee of the CPC, with Comrade Xi Jinping as its core, has adhered to the people's position of discourse, and has constructed ideological discourse such as China's dream, building a well-off society in an all-round way, accurately helping the poor, and building and sharing together. It has guided the people's livelihood as the guide and has launched the Ideological Expression of practice and won the recognition of the people.

The reason why a theory is widely accepted and recognized by people does not lie in the self flaunting of the theory, but in the fact that it can provide the content that meets people's needs and the way that is easy to understand, and has certain attraction and appeal.

From the founding of new China to before the reform and opening up, the construction of ideological discourse power of the Communist Party of China mainly relies on political authority, with the help of theoretical indoctrination to complete and realize. Overemphasizing and relying on the role of ideology, while ignoring the psychological characteristics and interest needs of people at all levels of society, will inevitably lead to the embarrassing situation of mainstream ideology. After the reform and opening up, the narrative mode of the mainstream ideology has changed significantly. Before the reform and opening up, the "revolutionary and mobilizing" narrative has gradually turned to the "constructive and living" narrative, which better meets the psychological needs of the audience. In today's mobile Internet era, new changes have taken place in the convenience, interactivity, magnanimity and timeliness of social subjects' receiving, sharing and feedback information resources. Ideological propaganda work should deeply analyze the differences between Internet communication and traditional media communication, carefully plan and innovate communication contents, methods and means, and build a fit under the guidance of mainstream ideology The popularization, interaction and differentiation communication platform of audience demand.

The construction of mainstream ideological discourse power can only be close to the needs of the public, and can be accepted sincerely by the people in real life.

II. Enlightenment from the construction of ideological discourse power in the 70 years since the founding of new China

Reviewing the history of the construction of socialist ideological discourse power since the founding of new China, this process is a process of continuation in inheritance, development in innovation and improvement in summary.

Since the founding of new China 70 years ago, the theory and practice of ideological discourse right have made historic achievements. However, due to the influence of various factors at home and abroad, there have been some mistakes in the construction of ideological discourse right. It is of great significance to seriously summarize the achievements and valuable experience in this historical stage.

2.1 The construction of ideological discourse power must conform to the development direction of the times and adhere to the problem orientation.

"Adhering to problem orientation is a distinctive feature of Marxism [12]." If an ideology can not only reflect the law and direction of the development of human society, but also help people to solve the main problems and difficulties they are facing. It not only conforms to the desire of the poor people to urgently change the social and survival status quo, but also points out a bright road for them to liberate themselves, then this ideology will be selected and accepted by the majority of people in the society, so as to truly achieve the goal To win the discourse power of ideology dominated by society. The Communist Party of China should always pay attention to people's livelihood, adhere to people-oriented, take the road of scientific development, constantly improve and effectively protect people's livelihood, and enable the people to share the results of reform. Only in this way can we fundamentally solve the problem of identity of mainstream ideology and construct the leading role of Marxist Discourse Power in contemporary social thoughts.

In the period of socialist construction, the focus of the construction of discourse power is to talk about the inevitability of socialist transformation. In the period of Deng Xiaoping theory, the focus of the construction of discourse power is to talk about the essence of socialism. In order to do a good job in the construction of ideological discourse power in today's China, we must talk about the "Chinese road", "Chinese theory", "Chinese system" and "Chinese culture". Only the mainstream ideological discourse based on practice can win the trust of the people.

2.2 Adhere to the innovation of the construction of ideological discourse power

Innovation is the inevitable requirement of ideological work, promoting all-round innovation in concept, content, means, system and mechanism. The idea innovation is to keep the openness of thought, break the traditional thinking pattern, and open a new situation of ideological discourse work with a new leap of ideological understanding. The construction of ideology is primarily the construction of Chinese discourse, and the core of Chinese discourse construction is the construction of Chinese theory [13]. Only by constructing this theory can we really build the Chinese discourse and Chinese discourse system based on this theory, solve the so-called "three lost" problem, occupy the main position of Chinese ideology, and resist the infiltration of Western ideology. Innovative methods and means are to speed up the development of media convergence, give full play to the advantages of new media technology, and occupy the commanding height of information communication.

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